

26355 Grueber – Photometric Re-Analysis Report

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1. Introduction

This report summarizes the photometric re-analysis of asteroid **26355 Grueber**.

2. Data Summary

- Number of data points: 52
- Observing nights: N/A
- Filters: R/Clear
- Time span: 2455881.01211 - 2456116.7205

3. Primary Period Analysis

3.1 Periodogram

Figure 1: Primary periodogram

3.2 Phase Plot ($P = 24.0476$ h)

Figure 2: Primary phase

3.3 Residuals

4. Secondary Period Search

4.1 Residual Periodogram

4.2 Phase Plot (candidate)

5. Discussion

- Evidence strength
- Possible aliasing
- Compatibility with literature

6. Conclusions

Primary period confirmed as **24.0476 h**.
Secondary period remains a **candidate**.

Figure 4: Secondary periodogram

Figure 5: Secondary phase